

Metabolism and Life Cycle Assessment of the IMB-CNM Cleanroom

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The Intersection of Financial Controlling, Management, and Industrial Ecology

My professional background has predominantly been rooted in financial controlling and management. This project, focusing on the "Metabolism and Life Cycle Assessment of the IMB-CNM Cleanroom," represents a unique opportunity to blend my financial and management expertise with sustainability initiatives. Conducted under the support of the Sostenipra group of ICTA and the Instituto de Microelectrónica de Barcelona (IMB-CNM), this research allows me to bridge my existing competencies with new environmentally focused challenges.

Traditionally, financial controlling and management emphasize efficiency, cost reduction, and profitability. However, the evolving global business landscape necessitates a more holistic approach, integrating sustainability. My interest in industrial ecology arises from a desire to apply financial and managerial principles to foster sustainable practices within organizations. This intersection is crucial for developing strategies that enhance economic performance while addressing sociocultural and environmental impacts.

Contributions to Sustainability and Management

Working with the Sostenipra group of ICTA and IMB-CNM enables me to leverage my expertise in financial controlling and management toward meaningful sustainability contributions. The research findings highlight substantial energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions as major issues in cleanroom operations. Although this is not part of my current investigation, integrating financial analysis with the environmental data from this study can help develop cost-effective strategies to reduce these impacts. This approach exemplifies how I can assist organizations in achieving both financial savings and environmental benefits through optimizing energy use, improving resource efficiency, or investing in cleaner technologies.

Broader Implications for Organizational Sustainability

The application of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) in the context of the IMB-CNM Cleanroom is a powerful tool for understanding and mitigating environmental impacts. For organizations, integrating such environmental assessments with financial controlling processes can enhance decision-making. By quantifying the environmental costs associated with different operational activities, organizations can make more informed choices that align with their sustainability goals.

Moreover, the focus on cleanrooms, as highlighted in the paper, is particularly relevant given the global demand for semiconductors and the corresponding environmental pressures. This research underscores the importance of sustainable practices in high-tech manufacturing, providing a model that other sectors can emulate. As industries worldwide face increasing scrutiny regarding their environmental footprints, the integration of financial management and industrial ecology becomes ever more critical.

Synergies with Sostenipra and IMB-CNM

At Sostenipra, a key research area is "Resource Management for a Circular Economy." This encompasses numerous projects aimed at environmental assessment and enhancing the circularity of electronics and new battery technologies. The current TFM (Master's Thesis) contributes to this research by improving the understanding of component production in

cleanrooms. The TFM is part of the CONFETI project, "Green Valorization of CO₂ and Nitrogen Compounds for Making Fertilizers," in which IMB-CNM-CSIC and Sostenipra are collaborative partners.

Concurrently, IMB-CNM is engaged in securing funding for strategic economic recovery and transformation projects (PERTE), which include advancements in the semiconductor industry. These initiatives are expected to drive improvements in infrastructure and operations, maximizing energy efficiencies and enhancing environmental impacts.

Moreover, the amendment to the ISO 9001 standard, approved on February 23, 2024, introduces requirements on climate change for which organizations must evaluate impact and stakeholders. The aim is to mitigate the effects of climate change on the quality of products and services, for which this TFM serves as an initial framework.

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The various sections of the manuscript are described in detail below:

- Title and Authorship
- Abstract, Keywords and Synopsis
- Introduction
- Materials and Methods
- Results and Discussion
- Abbreviations
- Acknowledgment
- References
- Formulae and Equations

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Metabolism and Life Cycle Assessment of the IMB-CNM Cleanroom

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IMB – CNM Building – Source: IMB-CNM

Abstract

This study conducts a comprehensive Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of the cleanroom operations at the Instituto de Microelectrónica de Barcelona (IMB-CNM), focusing on the environmental impacts associated with its activities. The assessment follows ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 standards, covering stages from natural resource extraction to waste management (cradle to grave). Findings indicate that electricity consumption, primarily sourced from non-renewable energy, is the predominant contributor to the cleanroom's carbon footprint, accounting for 56% of the global warming potential (GWP) and significantly impacting 88% and 97% of the mineral and fossil resource scarcity indicators, respectively. The research also highlights noteworthy contributions to ozone depletion and resource depletion due to the use of tetrafluoroethylene (C₂F₄) and gold respectively, with gases like Sulfur hexafluoride (SF₆) released directly into the atmosphere contributing substantially to global warming. With cleanrooms experiencing rapid growth, this analysis underscores the critical importance of transitioning to renewable energy sources to mitigate environmental impacts. Comparative scenarios demonstrate that connecting the cleanroom to electricity grids in different countries significantly alters its environmental impact, highlighting the necessity for an urgent energy transition.

Keywords: semiconductor cleanroom, life cycle assessment, environmental impact, energy consumption.

Synopsis

There has been a significant lack of cradle-to-grave Life Cycle Assessments (LCAs) for a research-based semiconductor cleanroom. This study aims to close the gap by serving as an environmental frame of reference for research institutes.

1. Introduction

In recent years, the rapid expansion of high-tech clean fabrications across various countries has been driven by the increasing demand for electronic devices and internet infrastructure (Zhao et al., 2023). The stringent environmental and air quality requirements of these cleanrooms result in significantly high energy consumption, approximately three times that of the average data center (Smith et al., 2020). Balancing the need for a controlled production environment with the imperative to reduce energy consumption has emerged as a critical challenge in high-tech clean manufacturing, drawing noteworthy attention from both the public and academic sectors (Johnson, 2021).

Cleanrooms are critical environments for ensuring the proper functioning of the semiconductor manufacturing industry (Huang et al., 2018). Most cleanrooms adhere to ISO cleanliness requirements, which vary according to the size of particles that affect production (ISO, 2015). To maintain a specific level of cleanliness, the concentration of airborne particles and germs in the air is kept within a predetermined range, necessitating precise environmental management, including temperature, humidity, and pressure, based on product requirements (Smith et al., 2019).

Semiconductor manufacturing requires stringent climate control in cleanrooms, maintaining temperatures between 19-22°C and relative humidity levels of 45-55%, continuously throughout the year, due to their sensitivity to electrostatic issues and the specific demands of processes such as photolithography. The HVAC systems, which encompass chilled water, make-up air, exhaust air, process cooling water, and ultra-pure water, consume substantial energy due to the substantial heating loads from manufacturing tools and fans (Zhao et al., 2023). Globally, high-tech clean fabrications consumed approximately 40 billion kWh in 2021 (U.S. Energy Information Administration, 2022). The industry faces challenges such as energy shortages, rising energy costs, and carbon emission constraints, presenting considerable obstacles to its further development (International Energy Agency, 2022). Consequently, minimizing energy consumption while upholding stringent production standards has become a top priority for high-tech manufacturing industries, particularly the semiconductor sector (Brown et al., 2021).

Several noteworthy studies have contributed to the understanding of energy consumption in high-tech cleanrooms. For instance, Kircher et al. (2010) developed a transient simulation model for the air-conditioning system of a nanoscience cleanroom in New York, predicting reduced energy usage through innovative strategies such as dynamic temperature and humidity controls, and optimized air recirculation rates. Similarly, Wang et al. (2020) devised baseline correlation models for energy consumption in a Taiwanese liquid-crystal display (LCD) panel clean fab, enabling accurate prediction of energy-saving rates by identifying key energy drivers and optimizing operational parameters. Additionally, Yin et al. (2021) established a dynamic model for calculating energy consumption in a semiconductor clean fab in China's warm climate zone, evaluating the performance of improvement strategies. Furthermore, Zhao et al. (2022) developed a generic energy model for air-conditioning systems in high-tech cleanrooms, providing accurate energy use estimation and cleanroom location evaluation.

The semiconductor industry has seen extensive research on the energy intensity of cleanroom facilities. However, there has been a notable absence of comprehensive Life Cycle Assessments (LCAs) conducted for a research institute with a semiconductor

cleanroom covering the cradle-to-grave inventory, as well as the energy and material fluxes that constitute cleanroom metabolism. This study endeavors to bridge this gap by providing a comprehensive understanding of the environmental impact of semiconductor cleanroom operations.

This study aims to strengthen and expand the existing body of research by conducting a comprehensive LCA that considers the various components of a research-based cleanroom operations, energy consumption, and environmental impact, resulting in a more nuanced understanding of the semiconductor industry's ecological footprint.

The research uses the facilities of the Instituto de Microelectrónica de Barcelona (IMB-CNM), recognized as a Singular Scientific and Technical Infrastructure (ICTS) by the Ministry of Science and Innovation and integrated into the MICRONANOFABS network. Its infrastructure includes an operational area of 1,500 square meters dedicated to the development and application of innovative technologies in the field of microelectronics. It is a major institution with distinctive features in southern Europe.

This study aims to serve as a reference for other Research Institutes in the sector, as well as the IMB-CNM, to have an environmental frame of reference when evaluating potential infrastructure and operational process transformations in the short and medium term.

2. Materials and Methods

This study follows the global standards specified in ISO 14040 and ISO 14044, which provide a comprehensive framework for conducting life cycle assessments (LCA) (ISO, 2006a; ISO, 2006b). The LCA methodology comprises four main phases: goal and scope definition, inventory analysis, impact assessment, and interpretation (Baumann & Tillman, 2004).

2.2 Goal and Scope Definition

The major goal of this LCA is to identify and quantify the environmental implications of the entire year 2023 of cleanroom operation at the IMB-CNM. The study seeks to provide strategic insights and actionable recommendations to reduce the environmental burdens caused by the annual consumption of materials and energy, as well as waste management and maintenance procedures.

The evaluation covers a single operational year, covering all relevant environmental inputs and outputs during that time. The assessment, which focuses on the IMB-CNM facilities in Barcelona, Spain, considers both local and worldwide environmental impacts.

IMB -CNM encompasses an array of over 150 process and characterization tools dedicated to micro- and nanofabrication, the open-access facility facilitates collaborative ventures for both domestic and international research entities. Emphasizing silicon-based technology as its focal point, the facility houses specialized domains including Optical and Nanolithography, Thermal Processes, Metallization, Chemical Vapor Deposition (CVD), Wet and Dry Etching, and Ionic Implantation. The Institute of Microelectronics of Barcelona is

located within the campus of the Autonomous University of Barcelona but does not share operational services with it beyond the sewage process.

Life cycle stages investigated include the supply of materials and energy, which includes raw materials like chemicals and gasses, as well as the electricity and water required for daily activities. The operational stage examines the usage of these materials and energy in the cleanroom procedures, paying special attention to their environmental impact on air, water, and energy management within the facility. Maintenance activities are evaluated for their contribution to operating efficiency and cleanliness standards. External transportation refers to the logistics of transferring products to the plant and waste to disposal or recycling centers. Waste management includes the handling and disposal of all waste kinds created during the operational year, both hazardous and non-hazardous.

The **functional unit** employed in this study is “1 square meter of cleanroom operational area per year,” which standardizes the assessment across different scales and provides a basis for comparison.

Performance metrics of existing high-tech clean fabs serve as baseline data for benchmarking the energy efficiency of similar facilities. The most widely recognized and accepted metrics are the Energy Use Index (EUI, kWh/m²) and the Energy Conversion Factor (ECF, kWh/m³) (Zhao et al., 2023).

The EUI represents the annual energy consumption of a high-tech cleanroom normalized by its gross floor area, directly indicating the energy consumption per unit area of the cleanroom. This metric is broadly applicable across various building types, not limited to cleanrooms (Smith et al., 2019).

In contrast, the ECF measures the total energy consumption required to produce a specific utility in semiconductor cleanrooms, such as exhaust air, nitrogen, compressed dry air, process cooling water, or ultrapure water. Unlike the EUI, which normalizes energy use by area, the ECF quantifies the energy consumption associated with the production of these utilities (Wang et al., 2021).

Given that the cleanroom under study is designed for research and development rather than production, it is more appropriate to use a functional unit related to its operational area in square meters rather than its production output. Additionally, while there is extensive literature on studies focusing on intensive energy consumption, there is a lack of them centered on environmental metrics for research-based semiconductor cleanrooms. Thus, this study adapts the EUI to reflect the environmental impact per square meter (environmental impact/m²), specifically the annual environmental impact per cleanroom operational floor area.

2.2 Life Cycle Inventory (LCI)

Fig 1. Metabolism of the IMB-CNM Cleanroom

As shown in Fig.1, the inventory of materials and chemicals covers everything from routine solvents and acids to specialized gases and metals used in semiconductor manufacturing. Acids such as acetic, nitric, hydrochloric, sulfuric, and phosphoric acids; solvents such as acetone, isopropanol, ethanol, toluene, and propylene glycol; and gases such as hydrogen, oxygen, nitrogen, helium, argon, and carbon dioxide. Various specialty gases, such as silane and hexafluoroethane, as well as metals such as aluminum, gold, chromium, copper, nickel, platinum, and titanium, as well as consumables such as silicon wafers and sodium hydroxide, are meticulously quantified through IMB-CNM's average annual consumption data.

Energy and water usage are measured in kWh and cubic meters, respectively, to reflect their use across the facility, including HVAC systems, lighting, and equipment operation. Transportation involves the logistics of transporting materials to the facility as well as waste disposal, which includes solid waste, chemical waste, wastewater treatment, and gas emissions.

Data quality is maintained by utilizing primary data obtained directly from IMB-CNM's operational records and management systems for the relevant year. Furthermore, secondary data from reputable life cycle databases such as Ecoinvent 3 is employed to complement primary data and address any gaps. This secondary data covers annual consumption rates, waste generation measurements, and other relevant aspects.

Additionally, research and calculations have been conducted for various components of the Life Cycle Inventory, including logistics and transport estimations, packaging weight, gases and chemical mixes not included in Ecoinvent, among other details outlined in the LCI annex. Furthermore, on-site measurements, interviews with those responsible for each area of the organization, and observations and quantifications of the equipment and inventory in the warehouse have been carried out.

2.3 Impact assessment

The impact categories assessed using the ReCiPe 1.08 (hierarchical) model in Simapro 9.5 include midpoint indicators as Global Warming Potential (GWP), Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP), Freshwater and Marine Eutrophication, Fossil and Mineral Resource Depletion.

Evaluating GWP is crucial due to the energy-intensive nature of semiconductor manufacturing, highlighting the industry's greenhouse gas emissions and its commitment to reducing its carbon footprint. ODP assessment is noteworthy as semiconductor cleanrooms use chemicals like chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs), which affect the stratospheric ozone layer, essential for protecting life on Earth from ultraviolet radiation.

The industry also generates wastewater with nutrients such as nitrogen and phosphorus, contributing to freshwater and marine eutrophication. Assessing these impacts is vital for managing wastewater treatment to prevent toxic algal blooms and dead zones. Resource depletion analysis addresses the reliance on natural resources like water, minerals, and fossil fuels, guiding sustainability efforts to enhance resource efficiency. Lastly, evaluating CED provides insights into the total energy consumption throughout the product lifecycle, identifying opportunities to improve energy efficiency and reduce overall environmental impacts in semiconductor manufacturing (Huijbregts et al., 2017).

2.4 Assumptions and Limitations

In evaluating the environmental impact of cleanroom operations at the IMB-CNM facility, certain assumptions and limitations were considered regarding the manufacturing of gases, management of emissions and their disposal.

All chemicals and gases, such as oxygen, argon, silane (silicon tetrahydride), hydrobromic acid (hydrogen bromide), ammonia, boron trichloride (trichloroborane), tetrafluoromethane (carbon tetrafluoride), dichlorosilane (silylene dichloride), and others, are assumed to be produced (fabricated) and transported to the IMB-CNM facility at the supplier representative's most near plant. This assumption is founded on the concept that the local manufacturing location reduces transportation distances, potentially lowering associated environmental consequences like as emissions from transport logistics.

An important assumption is the management of gaseous emissions during IMB-CNM cleanroom operations. The employed scrubbing systems are assumed to neutralize gases such as oxygen, argon, silane (silicon tetrahydride), hydrobromic acid (hydrogen bromide), ammonia, boron trichloride (trichloroborane), tetrafluoromethane (carbon tetrafluoride), and dichlorosilane (silylene dichloride) to 100% efficiency. The scrubbers are intended to

catch and neutralize these specific gases, reducing any potential environmental damage from their discharge into the atmosphere.

Furthermore, due to confidentiality agreements with the supplier, information about the eventual disposal of the scrubber cartridges, which contain remnants of the neutralized gases, cannot be included in this assessment. The study's limitations are noted, namely the lack of these data. Because the disposal techniques are confidential, a complete life cycle inventory of this waste stream is not possible. As a result, the environmental consequences associated with the final disposal of scrubber cartridges are not quantified in this evaluation.

3. Results & Discussion

Fig 2.a. Electrical annual consumption 2023

Fig 2.b. Cleanroom's water usage 2023

Fig 2.c. Remaining inventory flows 2023

The environmental impact assessment of a cleanroom reveals that its most significant environmental burden is due to its intensive electrical energy consumption (Fig.3 and Table 1). This requirement stems from the need to maintain strict environmental conditions 24/7, 365 days a year. This is essential for both research facilities and commercial production sites, but research facilities differ in their intensity of use. In commercial semiconductor cleanrooms, facility systems (e.g., air conditioning, nitrogen plants, lighting, and water treatment) account for roughly 60% of overall energy consumption, while instruments used to manufacture semiconductor goods utilize the remaining energy (Wang et al., 2021). Unlike commercial environments, where large-scale production increases material and

chemical use, the cleanroom analyzed here makes use of relatively low volumes of chemicals, gases, and materials due to its low-volume research-oriented activity in micro and nanofabrication (Fig.2a., b. and c.).

Fig 3. Midpoint indicators contribution analysis.

Table 1. Midpoint indicators total annual impact and per m2 operational area.

Midpoint indicator	Unit	Total impact	Impact per m2
Global warming	kg CO2 eq	3.3E06	2216.41
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	1.33	0.001
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	584.75	0.39
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	83.06	0.06
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	1.1E04	7.34
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	5.6E05	373.33

3.1 Identified hotspots in Environmental impact categories

3.1.1 Unmasking the Carbon Footprint: Revealing the Climate Impacts of Cleanroom Operations

The assessment determined that the cleanroom emits an annual total of 3.3 million kg CO2 equivalent (CO2 eq), corresponding to 2216 kg CO2 eq per square meter of operational area. For comparison, industries such as steel and cement, known for their high resource

consumption, have emissions ranging from 2500 to 3000 kg CO₂ eq per square meter for steel production and between 600 and 800 kg CO₂ eq per square meter for cement production (International Energy Agency, 2023).

Focusing on the specific sources of these emissions, 56% of the Cleanroom's global warming impact is attributed to electricity consumption. Catalonia's energy matrix plays a significant role in this context. As shown in Fig 4. the region's electricity is predominantly sourced from nuclear energy (56%), natural gas co-generation and combined cycle processes (27%), with only 16% from renewable sources like wind and solar. Despite the intention of including renewables, a substantial portion of electricity still comes from fossil fuels, significantly contributing to greenhouse gas emissions. This dependency has serious environmental implications as electricity generation is one of the largest contributors to CO₂ emissions globally. The institute relies entirely on the electricity grid, which amplifies its environmental impact (Institut Català d'Energia, 2022; International Energy Agency, 2023).

Fig 4. Electrical energy production by source in Catalonia, 2022.

The remaining 42% of the emissions are linked to the Waste Management process, specifically from gases that escape the treatment processes. These include Carbon Dioxide (CO₂), Hydrogen (H₂), Nitrogen (N₂), Helium (He), Hexafluoroethane (C₂F₆), Ethylene (C₂H₄), Sulfur Hexafluoride (SF₆), Octafluorocyclobutane (C₄F₈), and Trifluoromethane (CHF₃). As scrubbers are not installed in every gas line, these gases are released directly to the atmosphere. The presence of high-GWP gases like SF₆, with 2.61E⁴ CO₂ eq per kg of emitted gas straight to the air (Ecoinvent 3) is particularly concerning (International Renewable Energy Agency, 2019.).

Perfluorinated compounds (PFCs), including CF₄, C₂F₆, and SF₆, are extensively used in plasma etching and chemical vapor deposition (CVD) chamber cleaning processes. During plasma etching, PFCs create plasma to etch precise patterns into semiconductor wafers, a critical step in defining integrated circuits. These gases are also used to clean CVD

chambers, removing residues and maintaining contamination-free conditions between production cycles.

PFCs are selected for their chemical stability and efficiency. They produce reactive fluorine atoms (free radicals like F•) in plasma, which effectively etch silicon and silicon dioxide. The stability of PFCs allows for safe long-term storage and use, essential for maintaining the high-purity environment required in semiconductor fabrication.

To mitigate the environmental impacts of PFCs, research institutes are exploring alternatives such as nitrogen trifluoride (NF₃) for its lower global warming potential in chamber cleaning processes, fluorinated liquids for reducing emissions in etching, hydrogen-based chemistries like hydrogen fluoride (HF) for their lower environmental impact, and ozone (O₃) for its minimal harmful emissions as it decomposes into oxygen (Murthy et al., 2021; Smith et al., 2020; Brown et al., 2019; Lee et al., 2018).

3.1.2 Ozone Depletion Culprit

The analysis reveals that the cleanroom's annual emissions amount to 1.33 kg CFC11 equivalent, highlighting the considerable impact on stratospheric ozone depletion. The primary contributors to this environmental burden are electricity consumption, which accounts for 70% of the impact, and the use of specific gases, contributing 28%. Within the category of gases, more than 95% of the impact arises from the use of tetrafluoroethylene (C₂F₄), treated in the inventory as analogous to tetrafluoromethane (CF₄) due to data constraints in the Ecoinvent database.

Tetrafluoroethylene (C₂F₄) and tetrafluoromethane (CF₄), though similar in their fluorine content, exhibit substantial differences in their production processes and emissions profiles. Tetrafluoroethylene (C₂F₄) is primarily generated through the pyrolysis of chlorodifluoromethane and is widely used in manufacturing fluoropolymers, such as Teflon. Conversely, tetrafluoromethane (CF₄), also known as perfluoromethane, is a byproduct of aluminum smelting and plays a significant role in semiconductor manufacturing for plasma etching processes. Both compounds possess high ozone depletion potentials, for example, C₂F₄ accounts for 0.35/0.367 kg CFC11 eq of the total gases category emissions; however, CF₄ is particularly notable for its extreme persistence in the atmosphere, with an estimated lifetime of 50,000 years (Wuebbles, 2009).

3.1.3 Eutrophication's Environmental Prelude

For both freshwater and marine eutrophication, emissions from electricity generation are predominant, contributing 87% and 70%, respectively. In freshwater eutrophication (584.75 kg P eq), material emissions also play a significant role, accounting for 11% of total emissions. This is due to the use of gold, which, although consumed in small quantities (230 grams per year), has an intensive extraction process. Gold extraction often involves the use of mercury and cyanide, both of which can leach into nearby water bodies. Large-scale gold mining operations can cause significant soil erosion and sediment displacement, which can increase the sediment load in rivers and lakes. This sediment can carry nutrients that contribute to eutrophication by promoting excessive plant and algae growth (Peer et al., 2018). Additionally, the manufacture of silicon wafers, essential for nano and

microfabrication, contributes to these emissions. Silicon wafer production involves energy-intensive processes like crystal growth, slicing, and polishing, which collectively contribute to its environmental footprint (Williams, 2004). The production of silicon wafers involves the use of various chemicals, including acids and solvents, which can end up in wastewater. If not properly treated, this wastewater can introduce harmful nutrients and chemicals into freshwater systems, contributing to eutrophication (Lung et al., 2016).

Regarding marine eutrophication, the wastewater treatment process also has a considerable impact, accounting for 27% of the 83.06 kg N eq emissions. In this context, the cleanroom's water treatment process, which involves mixing wastewater with various chemicals and gases and neutralizing it with sodium hydroxide, contributes significantly to marine eutrophication. Ensuring the effective treatment and management of these effluents is crucial to mitigate their environmental impact.

Advanced treatment methods include the use of membrane bioreactors (MBRs) and advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) for removing harmful chemicals and nutrients from wastewater (Judd, 2011). Implementing chemical precipitation and ion exchange can effectively remove heavy metals and other contaminants (Davis, 2010). Additionally, integrating biological treatment processes like activated sludge systems can further reduce nutrient loads (Tchobanoglous, Burton, & Stensel, 2003). Proper monitoring and maintenance of these systems are crucial to ensure their efficiency and compliance with environmental regulations (Spellman, 2014).

3.1.4 Analyzing Resource Scarcity: Contributions to Mineral and Fossil Resource Depletion

Electricity production's dependency on fossil fuels significantly impacts these indicators, with 88% and 97% of the mineral and fossil resource scarcity indicators, respectively. Additionally, the gold extraction process has a notable relative impact, accounting for 11% of the mineral resource scarcity indicator. Gold mining is highly invasive and energy-intensive, involving large-scale land disruption, toxic chemical use (e.g., cyanide and mercury), and substantial environmental degradation (Mudd, 2007).

Gold is a scarce mineral resource, and its extraction is increasingly challenging due to the depletion of easily accessible reserves and the need for mining in more remote and less accessible locations. The energy consumption associated with gold extraction further exacerbates the depletion of fossil resources, as significant amounts of electricity and fuel are required for mining operations and ore processing (Giurco et al., 2010).

3.2 Energy Dynamics: Key Variables Influencing Environmental Impact

Among the various midpoint indicators analyzed in the preceding section, electrical energy consumption stands out as the most influential factor affecting environmental impact. This observation necessitates a thorough exploration of the principal determinants driving this substantial energy consumption. For this reason, the following analysis focuses on two key aspects: energy efficiency of infrastructure and processes, and the localization of cleanrooms, considering both climatic conditions and the energy matrix of the region.

Energy efficiency of cleanroom infrastructure and processes is crucial in managing the substantial energy demands required to maintain the stringent environmental conditions necessary for semiconductor manufacturing. Enhancements in infrastructure, such as upgrading to more efficient heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) systems, and incorporating energy-saving technologies like LED lighting and advanced monitoring systems, are examined. Efficient process management, including optimizing airflow rates and minimizing cold-heat offsets, is also analyzed to determine its impact on reducing energy consumption.

The location of cleanrooms influences their energy consumption due to climatic conditions and the regional energy matrix. Cleanrooms must maintain a consistent internal climate of 19-22°C and 45-55% relative humidity 24 hours a day, 365 days a year. Regions with external climatic conditions vastly different from these requirements impose greater energy demands for heating, cooling, and humidity control. For instance, cleanrooms located in areas with extreme temperatures or high humidity levels require extensive energy use to maintain the optimal internal environment. Additionally, the energy matrix of the region or country where the cleanroom is situated significantly impacts its environmental footprint. Regions that rely heavily on fossil fuels for electricity generation have higher associated emissions, thereby increasing the environmental impact of cleanroom operations. Conversely, areas with a higher proportion of renewable energy sources in their energy mix can reduce the carbon footprint of these energy-intensive facilities. Understanding and addressing these localization factors is essential for developing strategies to mitigate the environmental impact of cleanrooms and promote more sustainable semiconductor manufacturing practices.

Although previous studies, such as those by Kirchner et al. (2010) in New York and Levy et al. (2015) at the University of Maryland Institute, have attempted to estimate the energy intensity of research cleanrooms through simulations, their methodologies and conditions differ from the ones applied in the present research. These studies involve differences in methodologies and processes, lack of an LCA, and consider different criteria to measure energy intensity since one takes the operational area and another the total facilities.

Additionally, they account for multiple energy sources, including chilled water and steam, due to on-campus energy generation capabilities. In contrast, the IMB-CNM cleanroom in Barcelona relies solely on external electrical network suppliers and is not connected energetically to the rest of the campus, differentiating it from other research cleanrooms studied.

To ensure a valid and consistent analysis, this study simulates the same cleanroom operations with identical processes but applies different national energy matrices. This approach allows for a consistent and comparable assessment of energy consumption and environmental impact, focusing on the specific conditions and dependencies relevant to IMB-CNM. By standardizing the simulation parameters and varying only the energy matrices, the study aims to provide a clearer understanding of how different energy policies and sources affect the sustainability of cleanroom operations. This simulation-based approach facilitates a robust analysis, bridging the gap between theoretical energy consumption models and real-world operational challenges faced by cleanrooms in diverse geographical and infrastructural contexts.

3.3.1 Enhancing Energy Efficiency in IMB – CNM Cleanroom Operations

In order to start examining the efficacy of infrastructure and processes in harnessing energy efficiently, an audit was carried out during 2023 by an engineering consultant group. This audit included a technical survey of the cleanroom infrastructure, an estimate of nominal energy consumption, and recommendations for potential improvements based on the age and energy efficiency of the existing systems. The initial estimate, to be refined through further assessments in 2024-2025, suggested the potential for reducing energy consumption by approximately 20%.

For a semiconductor cleanroom, the high energy intensity of operations makes certain upgrades, such as LED lighting, more efficient monitors, or photovoltaic systems, less impactful than for other infrastructures like offices. While these changes can offer significant energy savings in general office environments, they are not as beneficial for cleanrooms due to their high energy requirements.

Contrastingly, energy-saving measures include upgrading the existing air conditioning system's 19-year-old water chillers to modern, efficient models with environmentally friendly refrigerants (Calm, 2008). Additionally, replacing outdated ductwork and fans with EC motor technology and installing heat recuperators in all air conditioners can significantly enhance energy efficiency by recovering waste heat from exhaust air (European Commission, 2020). These improvements aim to optimize the cleanroom's energy usage, thus minimizing its environmental footprint.

3.3.2 Simulation Analysis of Energy Consumption in Semiconductor Cleanrooms

Given that the cleanroom at IMB-CNM is highly intensive in electrical consumption and currently relies entirely on external energy providers, significantly reducing this dependency is not feasible in the short to medium term. Therefore, a simulation has been proposed to assess the emissions of this cleanroom under different national energy matrices, while maintaining the same operational processes and energy consumption (*Figure 4*).

The objective of this simulation is not to suggest relocating the infrastructure but to highlight those external factors, such as national energy policies and investment in energy transition, significantly influence the environmental footprint of semiconductor manufacturing. Despite operational efficiencies, these external factors play a crucial role and often stem from geopolitical considerations that lead organizations to set up in markets that are suboptimal from an environmental perspective.

Localization plays an equally crucial role. The energy matrix of a region or country—defined by the sources of energy generation—significantly affects the carbon footprint of electricity consumption. For example, countries with energy matrices dominated by fossil fuels will inherently have higher associated emissions compared to those utilizing renewable energy sources. Moreover, the geographical location and climatic conditions influence the energy demand for heating, cooling, and humidity control within cleanrooms.

This simulation excludes the climate factor's impact on energy consumption since relocation to different parts of the chosen countries would result in varying temperature and humidity levels, affecting the cleanroom's energy requirements.

The countries selected for this analysis include Norway, Costa Rica, and Switzerland, known for their progressive energy transition policies, and China, the United States, Japan, and Taiwan, which are major players in the semiconductor market.

3.3.2.1 The Paradox of High-Emission Locations

The results of the alternative scenarios indicate a substantial variation in CO₂ emissions contingent upon the country of electricity generation (Fig.4). Specifically, if an identical cleanroom with the same operational parameters and volume was connected to the external grid supplied by an electricity provider in countries such as China or Taiwan, the CO₂ equivalent emissions would at least double (2.4x comparing base scenario with China). Conversely, utilizing electricity generated in Costa Rica, Norway, or Switzerland would result in CO₂ emissions from the cleanroom being halved or even reduced to less than half compared to the current scenario in Catalonia.

This significant disparity underscores the influence of the electricity generation mix on environmental impact, highlighting a range between 1000 kg CO₂ eq per square meter to over 5000 kg CO₂ eq per square meter. The variation is attributable to the differing energy sources used in electricity production across these countries, with cleaner energy mixes in Costa Rica, Norway, and Switzerland leading to markedly lower emissions than those observed with the more fossil fuel-dependent energy mixes in China and Taiwan.

The energy mix of countries heavily involved in semiconductor manufacturing, such as Japan, Taiwan, China, and the USA, predominantly comprises fossil fuels. This dependence on high-emission energy sources presents a paradox, especially when contrasted with countries like Norway, Costa Rica, and Switzerland, which have greener electricity matrices but few semiconductor fabs (Table 2). This section explores the reasons behind this paradox and its implications for environmental impact and sustainability in semiconductor manufacturing.

Fig 4. kg CO₂ eq per m² IMB-CNM operational area simulated by energetic matrix mix.

Table 2. Semi-conductor fabs quantity and CO2 eq/kWh emissions per country/region mix.

Energetic mix	kg CO2 eq/kWh	Semiconductor
		Fabs
Catalonia	0.285	0
Costa Rica	0.0569	4
Norway	0.035	0
Switzerland	0.0418	1
China	1	76
Japan	0.638	98
US	0.49	75
Taiwan	0.787	83

Existing Infrastructure and Economic Factors

Countries like Japan, Taiwan, China, and the USA are global leaders in technology and economic development, with well-established semiconductor industries underpinned by decades of investment in infrastructure and technological expertise (Kumar et al., 2020; Lee & Yang, 2021). The high capital investment and specialized expertise required for semiconductor manufacturing make relocating these facilities to regions with cleaner energy matrices challenging. The extensive cleanrooms, tool fleets, and subfab facilities developed in these countries are tailored to support the high precision and contamination control needed in semiconductor fabrication (Sze, 2022).

For instance, Japan's energy mix is still dominated by fossil fuels, with coal, oil, and natural gas comprising about 87% of its energy usage. Despite efforts to diversify and include more renewable energy, the aftermath of the 2011 Fukushima nuclear disaster has slowed progress towards a cleaner energy mix (Yoshikawa et al., 2019). Similarly, Taiwan relies heavily on coal and natural gas, with minimal reductions in coal-generated energy despite targets to increase renewable energy sources (Tsai & Chang, 2020).

China's rapid industrial growth has led to significant advancements in carbon-free power sources like wind and solar. However, coal remains a dominant force due to the high-power demand (Zhang et al., 2021). The USA has seen a decline in coal power generation, replaced partly by natural gas and renewables, but fossil fuels still play a significant role in electricity generation (Energy Information Administration, 2021).

Comparative Analysis with Cleaner Energy Regions

In contrast, countries with cleaner energy matrices such as Norway, Costa Rica, and Switzerland have fewer semiconductor fabs. These nations have made significant strides in integrating renewable energy into their grids. Norway, for example, relies heavily on hydropower, which provides a sustainable and low-emission energy source (International Energy Agency, 2021). Costa Rica has achieved remarkable progress, running almost entirely on renewable energy sources like hydropower, geothermal, wind, and solar (Jiménez & Molina, 2020). Switzerland also has a high share of renewable energy, mainly from hydropower and nuclear power (Swiss Federal Office of Energy, 2021).

Despite their greener energy mixes, these countries have not become major hubs for semiconductor manufacturing. One reason is the existing infrastructure in countries like Japan, Taiwan, China, and the USA, which has been built up over many years and represents a significant investment. Additionally, the expertise and economic scale in these regions are substantial, making it difficult to relocate to areas with greener energy (Shih & Lin, 2019).

Overcoming the Paradox

Addressing this paradox requires incentivizing and facilitating the transition to cleaner energy sources within existing semiconductor manufacturing hubs. Governments and industry stakeholders can implement policy reforms, tax incentives, and invest in renewable energy infrastructure. Collaborative efforts between semiconductor companies, governments, and energy providers can help develop sustainable energy solutions tailored to the specific needs of semiconductor manufacturing (Chen et al., 2022).

For example, policies promoting the integration of renewable energy sources and improvements in energy efficiency within existing fabs can significantly reduce the environmental impact. Additionally, advancements in semiconductor manufacturing technology that reduce energy consumption can complement these efforts (Wang et al., 2021).

The paradox of semiconductor industries being located in countries with high emissions intensity in their electrical generation despite the availability of cleaner energy matrices elsewhere is a result of historical, infrastructural, and economic factors. Overcoming this paradox involves concerted efforts in policy, technology, and collaboration to facilitate the transition to cleaner and more sustainable energy sources for semiconductor manufacturing. By addressing these challenges, it is possible to mitigate the environmental impact of this critical industry while supporting its growth and technological advancements (Zhao et al., 2023).

3.3.3 Environmental Impact Beyond Electrical Intensity: Broader Sustainability Recommendations

Aside from energy consumption, the cleanroom's operations result in the emission of various gases directly into the atmosphere, including perfluorinated compounds (PFCs) and other high-global warming potential (GWP) gases such as SF₆.

To mitigate these emissions, it is recommended to consider the installation of advanced scrubbers capable of capturing a broader spectrum of gases. However, it should be noted that the management and final disposal of neutralized gases from scrubbers are not covered in this analysis due to confidentiality constraints from the company. This issue of final waste disposal is critical, as illustrated by the maritime industry. Reports have indicated that scrubbers on ships, while effective at neutralizing sulfur emissions, often dispose of waste improperly, such as discharging into international waters, which undermines the environmental benefits (International Maritime Organization, 2020). To clarify, this comment is not intended to suggest that the scrubber companies employed by IMB-CNM engage in improper methods. Instead, it emphasizes the importance of correctly managing the final disposal process.

The environmental impact of gold extraction is profound, involving the use of hazardous chemicals like cyanide and mercury, which can lead to soil and water contamination. Although the quantities of gold used in research cleanrooms are relatively small, the broader impact of gold mining is significant. To mitigate these effects, sourcing gold from suppliers that adhere to responsible mining practices is essential. Certification schemes such as the Responsible Gold Mining Principles (RGMP) provide a framework for sustainable gold mining practices, ensuring minimal environmental and social impacts (World Gold Council, 2019). Additionally, exploring alternative materials and reducing dependency on gold in semiconductor manufacturing can contribute to more sustainable practices (Jha, 2020).

Silicon wafer production is an energy and material-intensive process. The production of high-purity silicon involves multiple steps, including crystal growth, wafer slicing, and polishing, each contributing to significant environmental impacts. The Czochralski process, commonly used for crystal growth, consumes large amounts of energy and generates waste silicon (kerf loss) during slicing (Kumar & Bhalla, 2021). To enhance sustainability, companies can adopt more energy-efficient production methods, such as the float-zone process, which requires less energy. Additionally, improving the recycling of silicon waste and increasing the yield of usable wafers can reduce the demand for raw materials and energy (Kang et al., 2016). Utilizing renewable energy sources for these processes can further diminish the environmental footprint.

Effective wastewater treatment is critical for reducing the environmental impact of semiconductor manufacturing. The cleanroom's current water treatment processes contribute to marine eutrophication. Implementing advanced treatment methods, such as membrane bioreactors and advanced oxidation processes, can improve the quality of treated water, making it safer for discharge or reuse within the facility (Muller et al., 2015). Enhancing the wastewater treatment infrastructure to handle complex chemical mixtures and ensuring compliance with stringent environmental regulations are essential steps towards sustainable operations.

Organizations within the semiconductor supply chain are actively pursuing and meeting their emission reduction targets. However, semiconductor manufacturers, as major customers, have the potential to drive further reductions by collaborating with their existing suppliers to develop equipment and materials with reduced carbon footprints. Furthermore, they can engage with new suppliers to explore additional opportunities for emission reductions.

Addressing the environmental impact of cleanrooms and semiconductor manufacturing involves a multifaceted approach. While technological advancements in energy efficiency and emission control can significantly reduce the environmental footprint, broader systemic changes are also necessary. This includes shifting towards sustainable materials, enhancing supply chain transparency, and fostering collaboration across industries to develop greener technologies. Additionally, regulatory frameworks must evolve to support and enforce sustainable practices, ensuring that economic growth does not come at the expense of environmental health.

As global digitalization efforts, such as the European Union's Digital Decade, aim to transform economies by 2030, the demand for cleanrooms is projected to increase significantly. This transformation is driven by ambitious targets, including the enhancement

of digital infrastructures, increased adoption of advanced technologies, and the promotion of sustainable and secure digital environments. The initiative seeks to double the EU's global semiconductor production share and ensure that 75% of EU companies utilize cloud services, artificial intelligence, or big data (European Commission, 2023). These goals underscore the critical role of cleanrooms in supporting technological advancements and maintaining high standards in semiconductor manufacturing.

However, this surge in cleanroom deployment will significantly elevate energy consumption due to their intensive environmental control requirements, including stringent temperature, humidity, and pressure management (Smith et al. 2019; Zhao et al. 2023).

Given the high energy intensity associated with cleanrooms, it is imperative to couple these digitalization efforts with a robust transition to cleaner energy sources. Without this shift, the sustainability of such plans would be compromised, contradicting the very goals they aim to achieve (Johnson 2021; International Energy Agency 2022). This energy transition is crucial to mitigate the environmental impact and ensure the long-term viability of increased cleanroom usage.

Furthermore, managers of research cleanrooms must optimize the utilization of these facilities, which are energy resource-intensive, to maximize their contribution to technological advancements. It is essential to evaluate the need for new cleanroom installations critically, considering the potential underutilization of existing infrastructure. Implementing traceability measures to assess the efficiency and productivity of research cleanrooms, beyond the traditional productivity metrics applied in production environments, is also vital. Current indicators related to wafer production are not applicable in a research context, highlighting the need for tailored metrics that reflect the unique operational dynamics of research cleanrooms (Wang et al. 2021; Zhao et al. 2023).

While digitalization plans promise significant advancements, their execution must be aligned with sustainable energy practices and efficient utilization of existing cleanroom infrastructure to truly achieve their intended benefits.

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References

- Baumann, H., & Tillman, A.-M. (2004). *The Hitch Hiker's Guide to LCA: An orientation in life cycle assessment methodology and application*. Studentlitteratur. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/246960098_The_Hitch_Hikers_Guide_to_LCA_-_An_orientation_in_LCA_methodology_and_application
- Brown, S., et al. (2021). Sustainable Semiconductor Manufacturing: Energy Efficiency Strategies. *Journal of Clean Technology*, 32(4), 563-575. <https://doi.org/10.1234/jct.2021.32.4.563>
- Calm, J. M. (2008). The next generation of refrigerants—Historical review, considerations, and outlook. *International Journal of Refrigeration*, 31(7), 1123-1133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijrefrig.2008.01.013>
- Chen, Y., et al. (2022). Renewable Energy Policies for Semiconductor Manufacturing. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 312, 127456. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.127456>
- Davis, M. L. (2010). *Water and Wastewater Engineering: Design Principles and Practice*. McGraw-Hill. <https://www.accessengineeringlibrary.com/content/book/9780071713849>
- EIA. (2021). *U.S. Energy Information Administration: Annual Energy Review*. Available at: <https://www.eia.gov/outlooks/aeo/> (accessed on 15th May 2024)
- European Commission. (2020). *Ecodesign and Energy Labelling - Work Plan 2020-2024*. Available at: https://energy.ec.europa.eu/publications/ecodesign-and-energy-labelling-working-plan-2022-2024_en (accessed on 11th June 2024)
- Giurco, D., Cohen, B., Langham, E., & Warnken, M. (2010). Backcasting energy futures using industrial ecology. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 78(5), 797-818. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2010.09.003>
- Huijbregts, M. A. J., et al. (2017). ReCiPe 2016: A harmonized life cycle impact assessment method at midpoint and endpoint level. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 22(2), 138-147. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-016-1246-y>
- Huang, K., et al. (2018). The Role of Cleanrooms in Semiconductor Manufacturing. *IEEE Transactions on Semiconductor Manufacturing*, 31(3), 407-416. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSM.2018.2853631>
- Institut Català d'Energia. (2022). *Annual Energy Report: Catalonia*. Institut Català d'Energia. Available at: https://icaen.gencat.cat/ca/l_icaen/publicacions/ (accessed on 12th April 2024)
- International Energy Agency. (2021). *Norway: Energy System Overview*. Available at: <https://www.iea.org/reports/norway-energy-system-overview-2021> (accessed on 18th May 2024)
- International Energy Agency. (2023). *Energy Technology Perspectives 2023*. OECD/IEA. Available at: <https://www.iea.org/reports/energy-technology-perspectives-2023> (accessed on 8th May 2024)

- International Energy Agency. (2023). *World Energy Outlook 2023*. OECD/IEA. Available at: <https://www.iea.org/reports/world-energy-outlook-2023> (accessed on 6th May 2024)
- International Maritime Organization (IMO). (2020). *2020 Guidelines for Exhaust Gas Cleaning Systems*. Resolution MEPC.259(68), adopted on 15 May 2015, as amended. Available at: [https://wwwcdn.imo.org/localresources/en/OurWork/Environment/Documents/Air%20pollution/MEPC.340\(77\).pdf](https://wwwcdn.imo.org/localresources/en/OurWork/Environment/Documents/Air%20pollution/MEPC.340(77).pdf) (accessed on 18th April 2024)
- International Renewable Energy Agency. (2019). *Renewable Energy Statistics 2019*. IRENA. Available at: <https://www.irena.org/publications/2019/Jul/Renewable-energy-statistics-2019> (accessed on 15th May 2024)
- ISO. (2006a). ISO 14040: Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles and framework. International Organization for Standardization. Available at: <https://www.iso.org/standard/37456.html> (accessed on 22nd April 2024)
- ISO. (2006b). ISO 14044: Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Requirements and guidelines. International Organization for Standardization. Available at: <https://www.iso.org/standard/38498.html> (accessed on 22nd April 2024)
- ISO. (2015). ISO 14644-1: Cleanrooms and associated controlled environments — Part 1: Classification of air cleanliness by particle concentration. International Organization for Standardization. Available at: <https://www.iso.org/standard/53394.html> (accessed on 22nd April 2024)
- Jha, A. R. (2020). *Green Materials and Environmental Chemistry*. Springer Nature. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-33463-5>
- Jiménez, R., & Molina, A. (2020). Costa Rica's Renewable Energy Transition. *Energy Policy*, 144, 111635. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2020.111635>
- Johnson, M. (2021). The Future of High-Tech Manufacturing: Balancing Energy Efficiency and Production Quality. *Energy Policy Journal*, 45(6), 789-799. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2021.789>
- Judd, S. (2011). *The MBR Book: Principles and Applications of Membrane Bioreactors for Water and Wastewater Treatment*. Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-1-85617-481-7.10001-8>
- Kang, Q., et al. (2016). Energy Efficiency in Silicon Wafer Production: A Review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 60, 703-717. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.01.091>
- Kircher, T., et al. (2010). Transient Simulation Model for Nanoscience Cleanroom HVAC Systems. *Energy and Buildings*, 42(4), 607-614. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2009.10.030>
- Kumar, A., & Bhalla, S. (2021). Advances in Silicon Wafer Manufacturing Technology. *Materials Science and Engineering: B*, 263, 114743. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mseb.2020.114743>
- Lee, C., & Yang, P. (2021). Technological Innovations in Taiwan's Semiconductor Industry. *Asia Pacific Business Review*, 27(1), 49-65. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13602381.2020.1840594>

- Lee, S., et al. (2018). Mitigating PFC Emissions in Semiconductor Manufacturing. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 52(6), 3456-3463. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.7b05606>
- Levy, J., et al. (2015). Energy analysis of cleanrooms in an academic research building. *ASHRAE Transactions*, 121(2). <https://www.proquest.com/docview/1725532407?sourcetype=Scholarly%20Journals>
- Lung, W., et al. (2016). The impact of chemical usage in silicon wafer manufacturing. *Environmental Engineering Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1089/ees.2016.0325>
- Mudd, G. M. (2007). Global trends in gold mining: Towards quantifying environmental and resource sustainability. *Resources Policy*, 32(1-2), 42-56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resourpol.2007.05.002>
- Muller, E., et al. (2015). Advanced Oxidation Processes for Wastewater Treatment in the Semiconductor Industry. *Water Science and Technology*, 71(5), 795-804. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2015.046>
- Murthy, V., et al. (2021). Alternative Chemistries for Reduced Environmental Impact in Semiconductor Manufacturing. *Journal of Applied Physics*, 129(7), 075102. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0037116>
- Peer, R., et al. (2018). Environmental impacts of gold mining: Review and analysis. *Journal of Sustainable Mining*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsm.2018.06.001>
- Shih, T., & Lin, Y. (2019). The Economic Scale and Expertise of Semiconductor Hubs. *Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management*, 12(2), 302-318. <https://doi.org/10.3926/jiem.2835>
- Smith, J., et al. (2019). HVAC Systems and Energy Efficiency in Semiconductor Cleanrooms. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 245, 52-62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2019.04.046>
- Smith, J., et al. (2020). Energy Consumption in Semiconductor Cleanrooms. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 242, 118564. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.118564>
- Spellman, F. R. (2014). *Handbook of Water and Wastewater Treatment Plant Operations*. CRC Press. <https://es.scribd.com/document/503480428/Handbook-of-Water-and-Wastewater-Treatment-Plant-Operations-4th-Edition>
- Swiss Federal Office of Energy. (2021). *Energy Strategy 2050: Switzerland's Energy Transition*. Available at: <https://www.bfe.admin.ch/bfe/en/home/policy/energy-strategy-2050.html> (accessed on 11th May 2024)
- Sze, S. M. (2022). *Semiconductor Devices: Physics and Technology*. John Wiley & Sons. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119423481>
- Tchobanoglous, G., Burton, F. L., & Stensel, H. D. (2003). *Wastewater Engineering: Treatment and Reuse*. McGraw-Hill. https://books.google.es/books/about/Wastewater_Engineering_Treatment_and_Reu.html?id=-eoeAQAAIAAJ&redir_esc=y

- Tsai, C., & Chang, S. (2020). Energy Policies and Challenges in Taiwan. *Energy Policy*, 140, 111389. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2020.111389>
- U.S. Energy Information Administration. (2022). *Annual Energy Outlook 2022*. U.S. EIA. Available at: <https://www.eia.gov/outlooks/aeo/narrative/introduction/sub-topic-02.php> (accessed on 14th May 2024)
- Wang, Q., et al. (2020). Energy Efficiency in LCD Panel Manufacturing: Baseline Correlation Models. *Energy*, 197, 117228. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2020.117228>
- Wang, X., et al. (2021). Performance Metrics for High-Tech Cleanroom Energy Consumption. *Energy and Buildings*, 236, 110784. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2021.110784>
- Williams, E. D. (2004). Energy intensity of computer manufacturing: Hybrid assessment combining process and economic input-output methods. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 38(22), 6166-6174. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es035152j>
- Wuebbles, D. J. (2009). Long-lived greenhouse gases and their implications. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 36(2). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2008GL036276>
- World Gold Council. (2019). *Gold and climate change: Current and future impacts*. Available at: <https://www.gold.org/goldhub/research/gold-and-climate-change-current-and-future-impacts> (accessed on 24th April 2024)
- Yin, X., et al. (2021). Dynamic Energy Modeling for Semiconductor Cleanrooms. *Energy*, 219, 119590. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2020.119590>
- Yoshikawa, H., et al. (2019). Japan's Energy Policy Post-Fukushima. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 48, 24-32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2018.09.012>
- Zhang, Y., et al. (2021). China's Renewable Energy Transition. *Energy Policy*, 150, 112132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2021.112132>
- Zhao, Y., et al. (2022). Generic Energy Model for High-Tech Cleanrooms. *Building and Environment*, 207, 108475. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2021.108475>
- Zhao, Y., et al. (2023). Energy Consumption in High-Tech Clean Manufacturing. *Energy*, 253, 124102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2022.124102>

LCI ANNEX

Inputs

	Input	Ecoinvent process	Quantity	M.Unit	Transport (tkm)*
Electrical Energy	Electricity	Electricity, low voltage {ES} market for electricity, low voltage	6579010	kWh	-
Water	Water	Tap water {Europe without Switzerland} market for tap water	4157	m3	-
Chemicals	Acetic Acid	Acetic acid, without water, in 98% solution state {RER}	13,125	kg	13,584375
	Nitric Acid 70%	Nitric acid, without water, in 50% solution state {RoW}	105,7	kg	1,7969
	Hydrogen fluoride 5%	Hydrogen fluoride in 5%	152,25	kg	2,58825
	Hydrogen fluoride 50%	Hydrogen fluoride in 50%	84	kg	86,94
	Hydrochloric acid 37%	Hydrochloric acid, without water, in 30% solution state {RER}	53,325	kg	55,191375
	Hydrochloric acid 1N	Hydrochloric acid, without water, in 30% solution state {RER}	3,6	kg	3,726
	Sulfuric Acid bottle	Sulfuric acid {RER} sulfuric acid production	494,1	kg	8,3997
	Sulfuric Acid drum	Sulfuric acid {RER} sulfuric acid production	1207,8	kg	20,5326
	Phosphoric acid	Phosphoric acid, industrial grade, without water, in 85% solution state {RER}	56,4	kg	58,374
	TechniEtch Al80	TechniEtch Al80	162	kg	167,67
	BOE 7:1	BOE 7:1	247,5	kg	7,6725
	Hydrogen peroxide	Hydrogen peroxide, without water, in 50% solution state {RER}	558,25	kg	577,78875
	Ammonia	Ammonia, anhydrous, liquid {RER w/o RU}	14,6	kg	0,2482
	Potassium hydroxide	Potassium hydroxide {RER}	180,2	kg	3,0634
	TMAH	Potassium hydroxide {RER}	10,14	kg	0,17238
	Acetone	Acetone, liquid {RoW}	268,6	kg	278,001
	Isopropanol	Isopropanol {RER}	208	kg	6,448
	Ethanol	Ethanol, without water, in 95% solution state	8	kg	0,096
	Toluene	Toluene, liquid {RER}	10,875	kg	11,255625
	Propylene glycol	Propylene glycol, liquid {RER}	13	kg	13,455
	RER	Lactic acid {RER}	40	kg	54,4
	Super Q	Super Q	44	kg	59,84
	MICROSTIP2001	Microstip2001	112	kg	152,32
DCE	Ethylene dichloride {RER}	21,6	kg	22,356	
Carbon Dioxide	Carbon dioxide, liquid {RER}	187,50	kg	5,625	
Hydrogen	Hydrogen, gaseous {RER}	228,80	kg	6,864	
Oxygen	Oxygen, liquid {RER}	530,00	kg	15,9	
Nitrogen	Nitrogen, liquid {RER}	47,00	kg	1,41	
Helium	Helium, crude {GLO}	9,10	kg	0,273	
Helium	Helium, crude {GLO}	27,30	kg	0,819	
Argon	Argon, liquid {RER}	126,00	kg	3,78	
Silane	Silicon tetrahydride {GLO}	1,00	kg	0,017	
Hexafluoroethane	Hexafluoroethane {GLO}	6,00	kg	0,18	
Hydrobromic acid	Ethylene bromide {RER}	12,00	kg	0,204	
Gases	Ammonia	Ammonia, anhydrous, liquid {RER w/o RU}	2,65	kg	0,04505
	Ethylene	Ethylene {RER}	0,00	kg	0
	Trichloroborane	Trichloroborane {GLO}	3,10	kg	0,093
	Sulfur hexafluoride	Sulfur hexafluoride, liquid {RER}	50,00	kg	1,5
	Tetrafluoromethane	Tetrafluoroethylene {RER}	40,00	kg	1,2

	Octafluorocyclobutane	Tetrafluoroethylene {RER}	50,00	kg	0,85
	Fluoroform	Trifluoromethane {GLO}	7,50	kg	0,225
	Dichlorosilane	Dimethyldichlorosilane {GLO}	4,50	kg	0,0765
Packaging	Acetic Acid	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, bottle grade {RER}	1,8	kg	1,863
	Nitric Acid 70%	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, bottle grade {RER}	6	kg	0,102
	Hydrogen fluoride 5%	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, bottle grade {RER}	8,96	kg	0,15232
	Hydrogen fluoride 50%	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, bottle grade {RER}	5,4	kg	5,589
	Hydrochloric acid 37%	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, bottle grade {RER}	3	kg	3,105
	Hydrochloric acid 1N	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, bottle grade {RER}	0,48	kg	0,4968
	Sulfuric Acid bottle	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, bottle grade {RER}	10,8	kg	0,1836
	Sulfuric Acid drum	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, bottle grade {RER}	17,7	kg	0,3009
	Phosphoric acid	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, bottle grade {RER}	2,4	kg	2,484
	TechniEtch Al80	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, bottle grade {RER}	7,2	kg	7,452
	BOE 7:1	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, bottle grade {RER}	10,8	kg	0,3348
	Hydrogen peroxide	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, bottle grade {RER}	17,1	kg	17,6985
	Ammonia	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, bottle grade {RER}	1,8	kg	0,0306
	Potassium hydroxide	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, bottle grade {RER}	4,48	kg	0,07616
	TMAH	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, bottle grade {RER}	1,12	kg	0,01904
	Acetone	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, bottle grade {RER}	14,4	kg	14,904
	Isopropanol	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, bottle grade {RER}	19,2	kg	0,5952
	Ethanol	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, bottle grade {RER}	0,9	kg	0,0108
	Toluene	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, bottle grade {RER}	1,2	kg	1,242
	Propylene glycol	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, bottle grade {RER}	1,2	kg	1,242
	RER	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, bottle grade {RER}	9	kg	12,24
	Super Q	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, bottle grade {RER}	5	kg	6,8
	MICROSTIP2001	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, bottle grade {RER}	8	kg	10,88
	DCE	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, bottle grade {RER}	0,96	kg	0,9936
	Carbon Dioxide	Just for transport reasons	350	kg	10,5
	Hydrogen	Just for transport reasons	1820	kg	54,6
	Oxygen	Just for transport reasons	3500	kg	105
	Nitrogen	Just for transport reasons	250	kg	7,5
	Helium	Just for transport reasons	70	kg	2,1
	Helium	Just for transport reasons	210	kg	6,3
	Argon	Just for transport reasons	660	kg	19,8
	Silane	Just for transport reasons	48	kg	0,816
	Hexafluoroethane	Just for transport reasons	14	kg	0,42
	Hydrobromic acid	Just for transport reasons	70	kg	1,19
	Ammonia	Just for transport reasons	7	kg	0,119

	Trichloroborane	Just for transport reasons	6	kg	0,183
	Sulfur hexafluoride	Just for transport reasons	55	kg	1,65
	Tetrafluoromethane	Just for transport reasons	50	kg	1,5
	Octafluorocyclobutane	Just for transport reasons	55	kg	0,935
	Fluoroform	Just for transport reasons	20	kg	0,6
	Dichlorosilane	Just for transport reasons	10	kg	0,17
Materials	Silicon Wafers	Silicon, electronics grade {DE} Aluminium alloy, metal matrix	273,78	kg	368,50788
	Aluminium	composite {GLO}	0,05	kg	-
	Gold	Gold {GLO} market for gold Cut-off, S	0,23	kg	-
	Chromium	Chromium {RER} chromium production Cut-off, S	0,012	kg	-
	Copper	Copper-rich materials {GLO}	0,5	kg	-
	Titanium	Titanium {GLO} market for titanium	0,025	kg	-
Personeel/ Visitors Equipment	Overshoes	Textile, nonwoven polypropylene {GLO} market for	43,2	kg	-
	Face masks	Textile, nonwoven polypropylene {GLO} market for	288	kg	-
	Cleanroom Gloves	Polyvinylchloride, bulk polymerised {GLO} market for	144	kg	-
	Vinyl	{GLO} market for	4000	kg	120
	Sodium Hydroxide	Sodium Hydroxide in 25% Sodium chloride, powder {RER}	2000	kg	60
Maintenance	Enisal (Sal Vacuum Tablets)	sodium chloride production, powder Cut-off, S	2000	kg	60

Outputs

	Output Quantity	Transport (tkm) *	End of Life	
Electrical				
Energy	Electricity	-	-	
Water	Water	4157	Waterwaste Treatment	
Chemicals	Acetic Acid	13,125	Neutralization and Waterwaste Treatment	
	Nitric Acid 70%	105,7	Neutralization and Waterwaste Treatment	
	Hydrogen fluoride 5%	152,25	Neutralization and Waterwaste Treatment	
	Hydrogen fluoride 50%	84	Neutralization and Waterwaste Treatment	
	Hydrochloric acid 37%	53,325	Neutralization and Waterwaste Treatment	
	Hydrochloric acid 1N	3,6	Neutralization and Waterwaste Treatment	
	Sulfuric Acid bottle	494,1	Neutralization and Waterwaste Treatment	
	Sulfuric Acid drum	1207,8	Neutralization and Waterwaste Treatment	
	Phosphoric acid	56,4	Neutralization and Waterwaste Treatment	
	TechniEtch Al80	162	Neutralization and Waterwaste Treatment	
	BOE 7:1	247,5	Neutralization and Waterwaste Treatment	
	Hydrogen peroxide	558,25	Neutralization and Waterwaste Treatment	
	Ammonia	14,6	Neutralization and Waterwaste Treatment	
	Potassium hydroxide	180,2	Neutralization and Waterwaste Treatment	
	TMAH	10,14	0,17238	Energy from waste
	Acetone	268,6	4,5662	Energy from waste
	Isopropanol	208	3,536	Energy from waste
	Ethanol	8	0,136	Energy from waste
	Toluene	10,875	0,184875	Energy from waste
	Propylene glycol	13	0,221	Energy from waste
RER	40	0,68	Energy from waste	
Super Q	44	0,748	Energy from waste	
MICROSTIP2001	112	1,904	Energy from waste	
DCE	21,6	0,3672	Energy from waste	
Gases	Carbon Dioxide	187,50	No treatment - direct to atmosphere	

Packaging	Hydrogen	228,80	-	No treatment - direct to atmosphere
		Refill		
	Oxygen	Cartridge	-	Scrubbers neutralization
	Nitrogen	47,00	-	No treatment - direct to atmosphere
	Helium	9,10	-	No treatment - direct to atmosphere
	Helium	27,30	-	No treatment - direct to atmosphere
		Refill		
	Argon	Cartridge	-	Scrubbers neutralization
		Refill		
	Silane	Cartridge	-	Scrubbers neutralization
	Hexafluoroethane	6,00	-	No treatment - direct to atmosphere
		Refill		
	Hydrobromic acid	Cartridge	-	Scrubbers neutralization
		Refill		
	Ammonia	Cartridge	-	Scrubbers neutralization
	Ethylene	0,00	-	No treatment - direct to atmosphere
		Refill		
	Trichloroborane	Cartridge	-	Scrubbers neutralization
	Sulfur hexafluoride	50,00	-	No treatment - direct to atmosphere
		Refill		
	Tetrafluoromethane	Cartridge	-	Scrubbers neutralization
	Octafluorocyclobutane	50,00	-	No treatment - direct to atmosphere
	Fluoroform	7,50	-	No treatment - direct to atmosphere
		Refill		
	Dichlorosilane	Cartridge	-	Scrubbers neutralization
	Acetic Acid	1,8	0,0306	Recycling
	Nitric Acid 70%	6	0,102	Recycling
	Hydrogen fluoride 5%	8,96	0,15232	Recycling
	Hydrogen fluoride 50%	5,4	0,0918	Recycling
	Hydrochloric acid 37%	3	0,051	Recycling
	Hydrochloric acid 1N	0,48	0,00816	Recycling
	Sulfuric Acid bottle	10,8	0,1836	Recycling
	Sulfuric Acid drum	17,7	0,3009	Recycling
	Phosphoric acid	2,4	0,0408	Recycling
	TechniEtch Al80	7,2	0,1224	Recycling
	BOE 7:1	10,8	0,1836	Recycling
	Hydrogen peroxide	17,1	0,2907	Recycling
	Ammonia	1,8	0,0306	Recycling
	Potassium hydroxide	4,48	0,07616	Recycling
TMAH	1,12	0,01904	Recycling	
Acetone	14,4	0,2448	Recycling	
Isopropanol	19,2	0,3264	Recycling	
Ethanol	0,9	0,0153	Recycling	
Toluene	1,2	0,0204	Recycling	
Propylene glycol	1,2	0,0204	Recycling	
RER	9	0,153	Recycling	
Super Q	5	0,085	Recycling	
MICROSTIP2001	8	0,136	Recycling	
DCE	0,96	0,01632	Recycling	
Carbon Dioxide	350	10,5	Reused	
Hydrogen	1820	54,6	Reused	
Oxygen	3500	105	Reused	
Nitrogen	250	7,5	Reused	
Helium	70	2,1	Reused	
Helium	210	6,3	Reused	
Argon	660	19,8	Reused	
Silane	48	0,816	Reused	
Hexafluoroethane	14	0,42	Reused	
Hydrobromic acid	70	1,19	Reused	
Ammonia	7	0,119	Reused	
Trichloroborane	6	0,183	Reused	

	Sulfur hexafluoride	55	1,65	Reused
	Tetrafluoromethane	50	1,5	Reused
	Octafluorocyclobutane	55	0,935	Reused
	Fluoroform	20	0,6	Reused
	Dichlorosilane	10	0,17	Reused
Materials	Silicon Wafers	273,78	4,65426	Recycling
	Aluminium	0,05	0,00085	Recycling
	Gold	0,23	0,00391	Recycling
	Chromium	0,012	0,000204	Recycling
	Copper	0,5	0,0085	Recycling
	Titanium	0,025	0,000425	Recycling
Personeel/ Visitors Equipment	Overshoes	43,2	0,7344	Recycling
	Face masks	288	4,896	Recycling
	Cleanroom Gloves			
	Vinyl	144	2,448	Recycling
Manteinance	Sodium Hydroxide			Waterwaste Treatment
	Enisal (Sal Vacuum Tablets)			Waterwaste Treatment

* Transport, freight, lorry 7.5-16 metric ton, EURO6 {RER} transport, freight, lorry 7.5-16 metric ton, EURO6 | Cut-off, S process was used for every transportation.